

REFLECTIONS OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN LAW AND FREEDOM, BASED ON SOME PRECEPTS OF THE DECALOGUE

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ABSTRACT: Reflections of the relationship between law and freedom, based on some precepts of the Decalogue.

We live in a society, where there seems to be a tension between law and freedom. Every man wants to live his freedom, but placed in a social context he is obliged to take the law into account. Similarly in the religious, spiritual field, some Christians believe that there is no law, while others say that there is a moral law, but that all values must be based on the law.

We note that from a social point of view, law regulates relations between citizens and between citizens and the state. From an ethical point of view, the law regulates human behavior, i.e. it tells us how to behave in certain situations. The two perspectives relate to law as a principle, as a body of rules, of established things, of norms, which society has accepted as important. From a religious perspective, from a Christian perspective, from a biblical perspective, if we want to be precise, the law is the character of God, it is the person's relation, not a set of rules. From an ethical and social perspective, from the perspective of our society, certain norms may change over time. While some Christians emphasize either the law or the absence of law, i.e. only freedom. The legitimate question remains, can the two notions, law and freedom, be reconciled?

Key words: *society, law, freedom, moral law, Decalogue, worship, conscience, religious freedom.*

Introduction

We live in a society, where there seems to be a tension between law and freedom. Everyone wants to live their freedom, but placed in a social context, they are obliged to respect the law. Similarly in the religious, spiritual field, some Christians believe that there is no law, while others say that

there is a moral law, but that all values must be based on the law. While some Christians emphasize either law or the absence of law, i.e. only freedom. The legitimate question remains, can law and freedom be reconciled?

The two notions, law and freedom, can be reconciled, although it is the emergence of the law that gave rise to the problems of freedom of conscience.¹ If we refer to the divine law, i.e. the Decalogue, it should not be forgotten that it required believers, those who obeyed it, to worship one God, at a time when the world worshipped many gods in polytheism, and until then it was not a problem with regard to faith, but when monotheism appeared through the Jews, it became a problem with accepting the faith of others. The divine law requires a different worship than the worship that was in that period, even though there were differences in worship even at that time, but they were all accepted, because eventually they all accepted the worship of multiple deities.

The Decalogue and freedom

The Decalogue demanded that worship be offered to only one deity and so this monotheism began to create tensions on the one hand. From another perspective, however, the Decalogue is the mode and condition of worship that the believer brings to God. When one accepts the God of heaven as his God, he accepts as a matter of life and death, as a matter of conscience, the law of God, and the moment he identifies his life with the divine law, then any external challenge that might prevent him from keeping the law and exercising his faith becomes for him a matter of conscience. If he yields to pressure and violates the divine Law, then he has a problem of conscience, which is why the question of law and the question of religious freedom are closely linked, and one cannot exist without the other.

We observe that from a social point of view, the law regulates relations between citizens and between citizens and the state. From an ethical point of view, the law regulates human behavior, i.e. it tells us how to behave in certain situations. The two perspectives relate to law as a principle, as a body of rules, of established things, of norms, which society has accepted as important. From the religious perspective, from the Christian

1 Marilena Marin, "Drepturile omului între abuz și nediscriminare" ("Human Rights Between Abuse And Non-Discrimination"), *Managementul Intercultural*, Volumul XVI, Nr. 2 (31), Braşov, 2014, pp. 209-213.

perspective, from the biblical perspective, if we want to be precise, the law is the character of God, it is the person's relation, not a set of rules. From an ethical and social point of view, from the perspective of our society, certain norms can change over time. There are laws that are given, there are laws that are repealed.

Thus, there are two aspects, namely the social, ethical aspect, linked to the law, and the religious aspect. When we talk about the religious aspect, we say that the law is the norm of divine governance, it is the divine character. And in our relations with each other as human beings, the rules of a human being's life come from his way of being, from his character. Thus the divine law is the mirror image of the divine character, since God cannot give a law contrary to his character, and in these circumstances the law, being a replica of the divine character, is an eternal principle, just as God is eternal, and for this reason the divine law is not abrogated after a certain period, since God is eternal.

The divine law represents the divine character, but it also regulates at the same time the way in which the creature relates to the Creator, which is why all God's rational creatures, creatures who have self-consciousness, freedom and the right to choose, relate to the divinity within the limits of His law, that is, in relation to His character.

We have to make it clear that there is a difference between the law as God's eternal principle, the law that applies to all beings in the Universe, for the fact that the divine government is universal, and He is the same on our earth and everywhere in the Universe, that is, He is unchanging, and on the other hand we have to accept that certain propositional forms of this revelation of God have to do with certain contexts in which they are put. For example in the Ten Commandments there is the prohibition not to covet our neighbor's ox or ass. Very many neighbors that we have today have neither oxen nor donkeys, There are also people, without exaggeration, who may never in their lives have seen what an ox or donkey looks like pulling and carrying burdens. Even if there are no oxen and asses in some people today, it actually tells us that the principle that is there is with eternal applicability. So the Ten Commandments are an exemplification, an explanation of the character of God in the context of our existence. God has given the eternal Sake principles so that we as humans can understand these ten practical rules that are easy for us to understand and apply, but the divine message that is intended is that the Ten Commandments have

universal applicability, even if some of the details we find in them are no longer as relevant to us as they were to those who first heard them.

The Ten Commandment law exists at the same time as God, existing even before the earth was created. The formulation in certain verbal patterns began to appear for us with the advent of man, and if we were to give a biblical example, Cain, the son of Adam, was rebuked, accused of murdering his brother. The moral law of the Ten Commandments was in operation at that time because murder was an offense under that law. There is evidence that the Jews celebrated the Sabbath before the Moral Law was given on Mount Sinai. There are many other evidences throughout the Old Testament that the people of God at that time knew the precepts of the moral law even before the giving of the law on Mount Sinai, certainly in a more empirical manner, the law being thus transmitted orally, because writing did not appear until the time of Moses, which is why we cannot refer to the divine law in a written form long before Moses, but it existed as precepts, kept by faithful people.

According to the Holy Scriptures, God the Creator shared with the first family, Adam and Eve, the precepts of His requirements or law, who in turn shared these requirements or God's will with their children. Some of the patriarchs were blessed with the gift of prophecy and received further revelations and instruction from God, which is why, although it was for everyone in the beginning, but from the time of the differentiation of religions, then it can be said that some parts of the populations of the globe did not know the will of God, and for this reason the extent to which they knew or were required to know the divine law comes into question.

The Bible says very clearly that where there is no law, there is no transgression², but if you look carefully back to Moses, you notice that God punished the people in the time of Noah, he punished the people of Sodom and Gomorrah, he punished Ham, the son of Noah. Why all this? If there had been no law to show that their deeds were evil, they were not punished, with the caveat that they nevertheless knew the precepts of the law, and knowingly chose to do otherwise, which is why we should be skeptical of anyone who makes claims that divine law was only known from Sinai onward.

The truth is that no society can exist without the regulation of relations between citizens, and this regulation or regulation of relations

2 Romans 4, 15.

between citizens is called law.³ It is impossible for a functioning human society to exist without certain relations, whether of coordination, subordination, or various other relations, between the members of that society, but if there is no scheme of relations between the people in a society, it cannot function.

The Decalogue and religious freedom

First of all, the Ten Commandments have shaped the ethics of societies throughout history, and in modern times we can observe that the principles of the Decalogue are found in most countries' constitutions and also form the basis of international law. As far as fundamental human rights are concerned, they can be found there: the right to life, the right to property, the right to family and others.

For this reason we can consider that practically the Law of God comes and revolutionizes human thinking, which begins to think in a profound way, when it comes to tensions between peoples, war, which means the loss of human lives, to kill or not to kill. But what interests a believer is how religious freedom relates to man's right to worship according to divine requirements but also according to his own conscience, i.e. how the individual understands divine requirements. From this perspective we can affirm that when one adheres to the worship of God, one implicitly adheres to the observance of God's law, and when one adheres to God's law, the believer yields part of his sovereignty to God, so that God's norm becomes a matter of conscience for man. When external pressure is brought to bear on certain precepts assumed by the individual, the individual will have to decide who is right, external pressure, public opinion demanding that he violate certain precepts assumed, or the divine word to which the individual has adhered.

The law regulates relations between citizens. When God created man, it was he who showed him what those ideal relationships are, between himself and his fellow men and between himself and God. After man's fall into sin, man sometimes considered that the plan that God had made for

3 Cristian-Vasile Petcu, „Cadru juridic al dialogului ecumenic creștin” („The legal framework of Christian ecumenical dialogue”), In volumul Simpozionului Internațional „Itinerario e il contenuto del formare ecumenico-studi ecumenici - Venetia”, Instituto di studi ecumenici S. Bernardino, Veneția, 2008, pp. 422 – 450.

his life, the relationships that God had regulated, were not the ones he wanted, and so he tried to make his own laws, his own regulations, which would favor him in his relations with others. In various cases the lawgivers may be tempted when they make certain laws concerning themselves or their families, but the only way to be safe is to always refer to God's law and make it the norm of our lives. The great lesson of the Scriptures is that God loves everyone and when he asks us to obey and keep his law, he is in fact inviting us to respect, cherish and love others.

Religious freedom has two aspects, one external and one internal.⁴ Religious freedom from the external point of view depends very much on how free you are as a human being within your being. The truth will make us free, Scripture says, the law of God is truth, and it frees me as a human being from the fear of the unknown, from the fear of wrong choices, from the fear of public opinion, from the fear of death, from the fear of civil authorities, and that is because in contrast to other authorities: the authority of the state, the authority of public opinion, I relate to divine authority. That is why divine law frees man from fear, giving him the power to cope with the possible pressures that may come upon him.

First, the first commandment of the Decalogue regulates authority. This is of great importance because it is important in life to know who has supreme authority, to whom you report and to whom you have certain responsibilities. In this context, we find it written in the first commandment that we are not to have other gods besides the true God, for it is He who relates to us in a personal way. He introduces Himself as the Lord your God, that is, a personal report and does not say: I am the Lord your God, but I am your God, the One who brought you out of the land of Egypt, out of the house of bondage, the One who did for you what you could never do. The Jews could never, on their own, have come out of Egypt the way they came out.

Another thing the first commandment does is that by regulating authority, it actually teaches us how to relate to others and to ourselves. The image we have of God influences the image we have of ourselves and of others. We see others and ourselves according to how we see God, because

4 Gheorghe Istodor,, "The status of the Christian - rights, freedoms, responsibilities - in an informational and digitized world. Missionary perspective", In *Journal for Freedom of Conscience*, Rotaru, Ioan-Gheorghe; Muşat, Dragoş (eds.), vol. 9, nr.1, Editions IARSIC, Les Arsc, France, 2021, p. 485.

the Bible says that we as humans were created in the image of God. If we see God as unforgiving we will behave in the same way towards others. Conversely, if we see God as One who is involved, as One who loves others, we will also show love and empathy towards others. This first commandment, which we find written in Holy Scripture, somehow underlies all the other commandments, regulating authority, but also how we relate to ourselves and to others in terms of how we relate to God.

If we circumscribe the first commandment of the Decalogue within the issue of religious freedom and look at it from this perspective, at first glance this commandment could be seen as an exhortation to intolerance towards those who do not accept God as their only God. On the basis of this understanding there have been many religious wars, claiming that those who do not believe a certain way have no right to exist. For this reason, it should be noted that the first part of the commandment (I am the LORD thy God...), emphasizes the fact that it is a contract in the sense that God has done a work for the Jewish people and for this reason the expression I am your God, refers primarily to the Jewish people, which he created and brought out of Egypt, and in a looser reading has also an application to each individual personally. God the Creator, did not bring out of Egypt individual persons one by one, but brought them out as a whole, as a people, and in this case it is a contract which God makes with the Jewish people, affirming to them the experience of deliverance from bondage, and that they as a people should not forget and remember that He is their only God.

At first sight, this commandment seems to have been only for a part of humanity, namely the Jewish people. It is true, however, that if we go to the fourth commandment, we notice that the Decalogue is for all mankind, being universalized, and there the commandment no longer speaks of you the Jew, whom I brought out of the land of bondage, but it speaks of you, whom I created. The address in the first commandment was to the Jewish people, and this aspect explains that God the Creator wished through the Jewish people to make an alternative to the communities that were around them and the other human communities, that they might see what it means for a human community to be patronized by God, to be subject to the authorities of God, and that this would make others to covet and have for themselves the spiritual as well as material well-being that those who are led, patronized by God or consecrated to God have, and on the other hand

it gives authority to those who are children of God, the chosen people, in order that they might present God in a credible way and that their mission might be accepted. For this reason, the slightly exclusivist character which appears at first sight in the first commandment must be seen in the light of its purpose, starting from the Jewish people to the whole of humanity, to bring all humanity on the right track of recognizing the authority of the Creator God.

Out of the house of bondage, out of the land of Egypt, the Jewish people were brought out, but today one might say that they accept that they, as humans, were created by God, but the house of bondage considers that it can no longer refer to those outside the Jewish people, enslaved in Egypt. If we take an overview of all the Ten Commandments, it is clear that they were primarily addressed to the people of Israel and for them the coming out of Egypt was a supernatural event, it was God's way of showing his power in the life of their community in such a way that no one could question the existence and work of God in their lives. Militarily, mathematically, strategically, as a handful of Jews, however many they were, slaves, in a pitiful condition materially and educationally, it was impossible for them to escape from one of the greatest powers in the world at that time. From this experience it is to be noted that God the Creator does for us something which it is impossible for us to do for ourselves, namely, He gives us the power to escape from ourselves, from the sin which binds us so strongly, even more strongly than the bondage of the Hebrews in Egypt, and the miracle of our deliverance from guilt, from various fears, from the things which hold us in bondage through various vices, is a miracle, in our opinion even greater than deliverance from a human bondage.

This aspect must also be seen in the light of the fact that in times when the Jews lived face to face with a polytheistic world, which put pressure on them and due to pressure from outside, various apostasies, that is, falls from their faith, falls that put them in a position to depart from the divine will. In this framework, going beyond deliverance from a physical, earthly bondage, the commandment universalizes the prerogatives towards a deliverance from every sinful state that can hold man captive to vices, lusts, feelings or attitudes.

In the course of time people have also accepted authority other than divine authority. Even Jews and Christians, who affirm that they are obedient to the divine will, that they are the people of God, have themselves de-

formed in their vision, in their understanding, the true God. David writes about this in Psalm 50: *“These things hast thou done, and I kept silence; thou thoughtest that I was altogether such an one as thyself...”*⁵

People come to create God in their own image and likeness, which can be seen in the kind of worship that exists today. There are many Christians in different religious communities who worship differently depending on how they perceive the divine. In this sense, Christians who want to be truly loyal to God must also bear in mind that globalization processes⁶ are currently seeking to standardize religion⁷, among other things, and are even exerting pressure in this direction. Regulations are also being adopted in various areas which, in a rather subtle way, conflict with divine requirements.

In His High Priestly prayer, the Savior in the Gospel of John⁸ raises precisely this issue. His faithful believers must form that community which is an alternative to every other human community we see in the societies around us. Jesus told his disciples that they must love one another.⁹

By affirming that the identity that exists between the three persons of the Godhead must also exist in the relationship between man and God, on the one hand, but also between man and man, the disciples could offer a viable model of peaceful living. Unfortunately, we often note that it is increasingly difficult to find this model, lived, implemented in everyday life, with the observation that in this area Christianity also needs a revival, a reawakening, perhaps even a

Christian responsibilities derived from the first commandment

It is observed that when God, the lawgiver says: *Thou shalt have no other gods before me.*¹⁰ He is not only referring to images, to gods, but He is also

5 Psalms 50,21.

6 Cristian-Vasile Petcu, *Relația dintre globalizare și identitatea Bisericii în contextul învățaturii creștine ortodoxe*, In „Teologie și Viață – revistă de gândire și spiritualitate creștină”, nr. 1-4/2023, pp. 90-100.

7 C. Mititelu, „The “Globalization Era” and the Right of the Church to Preach the Gospel to All Peoples. Canonical-Juridical Considerations and Assessments”, In *Ecumeny and Law*, 5 (2017), pp. 127-146.

8 John - Chapter 17.

9 N.V. Dură, „Dialogul teologic interreligios și regula sa de aur: „Libertas” et „in omnia Caritas””, In *Revista de Teologie Sfântul Apostol Andrei*, XI, 1 (2007), pp. 34-46.

10 Exodus 20,3.

referring to other acrid forms can be God to someone. I would emphasize one of those forms and that is selfishness and misunderstood authority. When God said to man: Thou shalt have no other gods before me, he actually said to man that he is not god...and in man's dealings with others it should be very clear that man is not god and that man actually worships God. God the Creator tells man to know that he is not god to others, but brother to others, and he must behave in this way, in the conviction that God the Creator works in the same way in the lives of others.¹¹ People of faith have a duty to witness to others that God the Creator can free them from themselves, from sin.

The authority to impose your own view or views on another does not come from God, who has always had a way of working that we should use, and if you look carefully, the Bible says so: *not knowing that the goodness of God leadeth thee to repentance?*¹², that is, God first shows kindness and then calls people to follow him.¹³

Conclusions

If we look carefully at the fact that when Jesus Christ was on earth, He mingled among the people, showed them sympathy, ministered to their needs and then called them to follow Him, a method that Jesus used, and we as people could follow this method,¹⁴ that is: to show sympathy, to show love, to show them a living faith and not a theory of truth. Another thing we could do is to talk to them about the image they have of the God they don't believe in, because sometimes we might discover that we don't believe in the God they don't believe in either. We might discover that they have a distorted image of God, and then it's normal that they don't believe in a God as they imagine it.

I believe that it takes patience to discuss with others to understand their point of view and to understand how we can build bridges between us. This method was also used by the apostle Paul when he went to Ath-

11 Samuie! Bălce, „Omul integru: Între libertatea conștiinței și o libertate responsabilă”, in *Jurnalul Libertății de Conștiință*, Vol.8, Nr.1, 2020, pp.568-580.

12 Romans 2,4.

13 Simion Belea, „Demnitatea și drepturile omului în cazul grupurilor expuse riscului de excluziune”, *Jurnalul Libertății de Conștiință*, Vol. 9, nr. 1, 2021, pp. 434- 452.

14 Samuie! Bălce, „Perspective ale comunicării în contextul crizelor sociale”, *Jurnalul Libertății de Conștiință*, Editions IARSIC, France, vol.4, 2016, pp. 375-388.

ens and began to preach there, starting from something they had in common, namely the altar¹⁵ he discovered, which was erected in the presence of an Unknown God. We may be surprised that even those who apparently don't believe in God may have certain ideas, certain conceptions that we can agree with and thus create bridges through which we can help them to understand why it is that we believe in God and what the God we trust and worship looks like.

Thus in the sphere of freedom¹⁶, the first aspect that we can deduce and understand from the first commandment of the Decalogue is that my duty as a man is to receive the revelation of the true God about Himself, to receive Him as my personal Lord and Savior and to worship Him. And, from another perspective, once I have received Him and believe with all my being that He is the God of all mankind, in that He created them and by creation all men are His, then it is my duty to promote religious freedom, to influence the creation of a framework favorable to religious freedom and the circulation of ideas, so that the message and knowledge about this one God is accessible to everyone. And, on another note, if I as a human being am aware that this is the truth, this truth will not make me conceited and think myself superior to others, but on the contrary it will make me humble, so that I can do as the Savior did, in the sense of sacrificing myself to come to the aid of others. And last, but not least, is the fact that it is only through community that this can be done, because God's plan to reveal himself to people presupposes a united community on the one hand¹⁷, and on the other hand, in this united community, the supernatural power of God to manifest itself and to make visible to everyone what it means to be and live under divine patronage.

When we study the Decalogue, we have two perspectives: the perspective of God, who says, and our human perspective, with the possibility of believing or disbelieving what He says. From God's perspective things are clear. The preamble to the commandments states the essence: I am the Lord God, which is non-negotiable, not dependent on human choice. He exists regardless of human choices. Man's relationship with God is of this

15 Acts 17, 22-31.

16 Emanuel Dobrin, *Valori umane și libertate religioasă*, In „*Jurnalul Libertății de Conștiință / Journal for Freedom of Conscience*”, Vol. 10, Nr. 3, 2022, pp. 380-387.

17 Cristian-Vasile Petcu, „Pacea și dreptatea după cărțile profeților mari”, In *Annales Universitatis Valachiae*, Facultatea de Teologie, Târgoviște, 2005, pp. 448-458.

kind: God is, and man is free to believe or reject God. That is the mark of man's freedom.

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